

PROBABILITY ANALYSIS FOR TENSILE STRENGTH
OF UNIDIRECTIONAL HYBRID COMPOSITES

V. Tamužs and J. Gutans

Institute of Polymer Mechanics
Academy of Sciences of the Latvian SSR
Riga, Latvian SSR, USSR

ABSTRACT

The paper presents the probability analysis for the tensile strength of a unidirectional hybrid composite, consisting of elastic high modulus (HM) fibres and elastic low modulus (LM) fibres of equal amount embedded in an elastic low modulus matrix. Both single layer and laminated hybrid composites are considered. It is shown, that at the beginning of failure the HM fibre breaks are accumulated. Various fracture modes may occur between the two extreme cases: a) alternately HM fibres and LM fibres break; b) only HM fibres break. The stress level at which the overstressed LM fibres are expected to break represents a lower bound on the hybrid composite strength. The damage level of HM fibres in hybrid composite is much higher than the damage level of HM fibres in HM fibre composite. Hybrid effect for strength is negative. Proposed method of analysis is applied to cross-ply composite.

1. INTRODUCTION

The fracture of hybrid composites has been theoretically studied in [1-4]. In paper [1, 2] the failure strain of a single layer hybrid composite (Fig. 1a) reinforced with high elongation (HE) and low elongation (LE) fibres of two types has been evaluated. In [1] the fracture criterion is a double break, consisting of an initial LE fibre break and an adjacent HE fibre break because of the stress concentration. Paper [2] proposes a certain modification of the model worked out by Zweben [1]. The fracture criterion is a double break, consisting of initial LE fibre break and an adjacent overstressed LE fibre break. In paper [3] the chain-of-bundles probability model of a single layer hybrid composite reinforced with HM and LM fibres of two types is considered. The failure strain and stress is derived from the probability of consecutive failure of at least 6 fibres of both types. The stress concentration factors are obtained by local load sharing rule.

Paper [4] presents the model of a unidirectional laminated hybrid composite (Fig. 1b), consisting of elastic HM fibre layers and elastic LM fibre layers of equal amount, embedded in an elastic LM matrix. The stress concentration factors in unbroken HM and LM fibres, mixed with a varied number of broken HM fibres or broken both HM and LM fibres have been obtained by the shear-lag method. The ineffective length has been calculated. Partially the model of a single layer intraply hybrid composite has been considered. In order to compare all the calculations have been made for a HM fibre composite. The given paper is the continuation of [4] with the objective to investigate the failure process of hybrid composite by taking into consideration the statistical properties of fibres.

2. MODEL OF SINGLE LAYER HYBRID COMPOSITE

The model of single layer intraply hybrid composite (Fig. 1a) consists of elastic HM fibres and elastic LM fibres of equal amount embedded in an elastic LM matrix. If the amount of fibres is different, then the fibres of greater amount are assumed to be a single fibre of greater diameter. Let us number fibres beginning with the arbitrary fibre. If it is a HM fibre, then 1, 3, -3, 5, -5, ... are HM fibres; 2, -2, 4, -4, ... are LM fibres. The ratio of Young's modulus of HM and LM fibres is $R_E = \frac{E}{E^*}$

Figure 1. The model of unidirectional single layer (a) and laminated (b) hybrid composite.

The strength of fibre is assumed to be random variable with the Weibull distribution function [5-8]. The cumulative Weibull distribution functions for the strengths of the LE and HE fibres of the ineffective lengths are given in the form

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left[- \frac{\sigma_h}{l_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^\beta \right] \approx \frac{\sigma_h}{l_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^\beta \quad (1)$$

$$F^*(\sigma^*) = 1 - \exp \left[- \frac{\sigma_h^*}{l_0} \left(\frac{\sigma^*}{\sigma_0^*} \right)^{\beta^*} \right] \approx \frac{\sigma_h^*}{l_0} \left(\frac{\sigma^*}{\sigma_0^*} \right)^{\beta^*} \quad (2)$$

where σ , σ^* are the axial stress levels on the fibres; σ_0 , σ_0^* the scale parameters; β , β^* the shape parameters, l_0 fixed gauge length, at which the fibres are tested, σ_h is the ineffective length of the broken HM fibre in a hybrid composite, σ_h^* is the ineffective length of the broken LM fibre in a hybrid composite.

At first is necessary to obtain the probability of random failure for each type of fibres under stress on a hybrid composite. The ratio of the random failure probabilities for the LM and HM fibres

$$R_p = \frac{P_1}{P_1^*} = \frac{F(\sigma)}{F^*(\sigma^*)} = \frac{\sigma_h}{\sigma_h^*} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^\beta \left(\frac{\sigma_0^*}{\sigma^*} \right)^{\beta^*} \quad (3)$$

By using the expression for fibre mean strength

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = \sigma_0 \left(\frac{\sigma_h}{l_0} \right)^{-\frac{1}{\beta}} \Gamma \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) \quad (4)$$

for $\beta = \beta^*$ we obtain

$$R_p = R_E^\beta \left(\frac{\langle \sigma \rangle}{\langle \sigma^* \rangle} \right)^\beta$$

According to [5-7] $\beta = 3+6$. For $R_E > 2$ $R_p > 8$. The initial failure of LM fibres is of small probability and at the beginning the HM fibre breaks are accumulated.

Two extreme fibre break propagation ways. The scattered fibre breaks are initiating stress concentration factors on adjacent unbroken fibres. In [4] the stress concentration factors have been computed by the shear-lag method. Let the HM fibre 1 be the random break (Fig. 1a). This causes the stress concentration K_i on adjacent fibres i , where i is the number of fibres. The probability, that at least one of the two overstressed fibres (i or $-i$) will break is

$$P_{i,1} = 1 - \left(\frac{1 - F(K_i \sigma)}{1 - F(\sigma)} \right)^2 \approx 2 \frac{\sigma_h}{l_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^\beta (K_i - 1) \quad (5)$$

for $i = 2, 3, 4, \dots$. The way that the fibre breaks are propagating depends on fibre parameters. After a random break of the HM fibre 1 the LM fibres 2, -2 or HM fibres 3, -3 may break. Various fibre break propagation ways may occur between the two extreme cases:

- a) alternately HM fibres and LM fibres break in succession 1, 2, -2, 3, -3, 4, -4, ...
- b) only HM fibres break 1, 3, -3, 5, -5, 7, -7.

It is necessary to investigate the conditions under which these two extreme fracture modes may happen. We can derive the ratio

$$R_{p_2} = \frac{P_2}{P_2^*} = \frac{P_1 P_{3,1}}{P_1^* P_{2,1}^*} = \left(\frac{\sigma_h}{\sigma_h^*} \right) \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^\beta \left(\frac{K_3^\beta - 1}{K_2^{\beta^*} - 1} \right) \quad (6)$$

where P_2 is the probability that a double break of the HM fibre 1 and HM fibre 3 will occur; P_2^* is the probability,

that a double break of the HM fibre 1 and LM fibre 2 will occur. The most probable fibre break propagation way is 1, 3, ... for $R_{P_2} > 1$ and 1, 2 ... for $R_{P_2} < 1$. Assuming $\beta = \beta^*$ we derive

$$R_{P_2} = R_{P_1} \left(\frac{K_3^\beta - 1}{K_2^\beta - 1} \right) \quad (7)$$

We have computed $R_{P_2} = 227 \gg 1$ for a single layer hybrid composite ($R_E = 5$, $\beta = 6$) and $R_{P_2} = 0.1 \ll 1$ for a single layer HM fibre composite ($R_E = 1$, $\beta = 6$).

3. SEARCH FOR THE MOST PROBABLE FAILURE MODE

Tree of probable fibre failure sequences. It is convenient to use the graph technique [9] to present possible fibre break propagation ways. Each point of the tree T (Fig. 2)

Figure 2. Tree graph T of the probable fibre break propagation ways of hybrid composite.

is the probability that the fibre, denoted by the number at the point, will fail. The HM fibres are denoted by odd numbers, the LM fibres are denoted by even numbers. We assume that the HM fibres break first ($R_{P_1} > 1$). Each path of length $n-1$ lines of the tree T shows different fibre failure sequence. The extreme left side path is the fibre failure sequence 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, the extreme right side path is the fibre failure sequence 1, 3, 5, 7. The root of the tree T is the first fibre break 1. The height of the tree T of $n-1$ lines depends on n the number of fibres under consideration. The fibre breaks are assumed to be propagating symmetrically against the first fibre break. The failure of a symmetric fibre is not shown in the tree. The path 1, 3, 5, 7 means 1, 3, -3, 5, -5, 7, -7.

Algorithm for searching the most probable failure mode.

Algorithm consists of the following main steps:

- 1) computation of the Weibull distribution parameters, calculation of the ineffective length and the probabilities of

initial random failure. When $R_{p_i} > 1$ arbitrary HM fibre is assumed to be broken (Let it be HM fibre 1)

- 2) computation of the stress concentration factors in unbroken fibres K_i for $i = 2, -2, 3, -3, 4, -4 \dots$ (by the shear-lag method [4])
- 3) computation of the failure probability $P_{i,1}$ for the overstressed HM and LM fibres i , (5)
- 4) searching for the fibre with the maximum probability of failure $P_{i,1}$
- 5) the fibre with the maximum probability of failure is assumed to be broken
- 6) transferring to step 2 until all $n-2$ fibres are broken.

The sequence of fibres with maximum probability of failure is assumed to be the most probable fibre failure propagation way.

Tensile strength of hybrid composite. Having found the failure mode we estimate the tensile strength of hybrid composite in the following manner:

- 1) computation of the probability that at least n fibres will break

$$P_n = P_1 \prod_{i=2}^n P_{i,1} \quad (8)$$

- 2) computation of the probability of having at least one defect containing a minimum of n broken fibres

$$W_n = 1 - (1 - P_n)^{MN} \quad (9)$$

where $MN = LN/d_f$ is the number of HM elements in the composite, L is the length of fibres, $2N$ is the total number of fibres of which N are HM fibres and N are LM fibres

- 3) computation of the tensile stress level on hybrid composite σ_{nc} at which at least one defect containing a minimum of n broken fibres will appear with the probability 0.5

$$W_n(\sigma_{nc}) = 0.5 \quad (10)$$

$$\text{where } \sigma_c = \sigma V + \sigma^* V^* + \sigma_m (1 - V - V^*) \quad (11)$$

and σ , σ^* , σ_m are the axial stress levels on HM, LM fibres and matrix, V , V^* are HM and LM fibre volume fractions

- 4) estimation of hybrid composite strength σ_c by computing σ_{nc} for different n

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow n_c} \sigma_{nc} = \sigma_c$$

n_c is critical crack length (number of broken HM and LM fibres). The damage levels of HM and LM fibres P_1 , P_1^* are obtained from (1, 2).

Calculations have been made for the single layer hybrid composite with the following parameters: fibre mean strength at the ineffective length $\langle \sigma \rangle = \langle \sigma^* \rangle = 4$ GPa, matrix shear modulus $G_m = 1.27$ GPa, $R_E = 5$, $E/G_m = 315$, $V = V^* = 0.25$, $MN = 10^5$. In Fig. 3 (curve 2) the calculations of the stress level on composite σ_{nc} are presented. The most probable fibre

failure sequence is 1, 3, -3, 5, -5, 7, -7, 9, -9, 2, -2, 4, -4, 6, -6 for $\beta = \beta^* = 6$. When $\beta = 6$, $\beta^* = 3$ the LM fibres begin to fail earlier. Fibre damage level $P_1 = 0.08$, $P_1^* = 10^{-5}$. The damage level of HM fibres in a hybrid composite is much higher than the damage level in HM fibre composite [5, 6].

Figure 3. Stress level on hybrid composite σ_{nc} (1, 2, 4) and ratio R_L (3) as the number of broken HM fibres n increases
 1 - upper bound on strength
 2 - calculations using algorithm of search
 4 - lower bound on strength σ_{Lc}

The hybrid effect for the hybrid composite strength is the ratio of the hybrid composite strength and the mean strength of a HM fibre composite and LM fibre composite. Negative hybrid effect has been estimated of -2%.

4. LOWER AND UPPER BOUND ON HYBRID COMPOSITE STRENGTH

It was shown that at the beginning the HM fibres broke. Afterwards the failure of overstressed LM fibres is more probable. The stress level at which the overstressed LM fibres are expected to break represents a lower bound on the hybrid composite strength. The strength determined by only HM fibre failure gives the upper bound on hybrid composite strength.

To find the upper bound on strength it is necessary to estimate the stress level on hybrid composite σ_{nc} as the number of broken HM fibres n increases. The fibre failure sequence 1, 3, 5, ... is assumed. From (1, 4, 5, 8-10) we obtain the stress level on HM fibres at which at least one defect containing a minimum of n broken HM fibres will appear with the probability 0.5:

$$\sigma_n = \frac{\langle \sigma \rangle}{\Gamma(1 + \frac{1}{\beta})} \left(\frac{\langle n^2 \rangle}{MN} \right)^{-\frac{1}{\beta n}} 2^{\frac{1-n}{\beta n}} \left(\prod_{i=3}^n (K_i^\beta - 1) \right)^{-\frac{1}{\beta n}} \quad (12)$$

σ_{nc} we obtain using (11, 12). Figure 3 curve 1 depicts the dependence of σ_{nc} on n .

In order to obtain the lower bound on composite strength

we should estimate when the overstressed LM fibres will start to break as the number of broken HM fibres n increases. Let n HM fibres ($i = 1, 3, -3, 5, -5, \dots, n, -n$) be broken. The probability that at least one of the $n + 1$ overstressed LM fibres ($i = 2, -2, 4, -4, \dots, n + 1, -n - 1$) will break

$$\text{is } P_{n+1,1}^* = 1 - \prod_{i=2,4}^{n+1} (1 - P_{i,1})$$

where $P_{i,1}$ is the probability that at least one LM fibre of the two (i and $-i$) will break (5). It is clear that

$K_2 > \dots > K_{n+1}$ [4]. Assuming $K_i = K_2$ we derive

$$P_{n+1,1}^* = (n+1) \frac{d_h^*}{l_0} \left(\frac{\sigma^*}{\sigma_0^*} \right)^{\beta^*} (K_2^{\beta^*} - 1)$$

for $i = 2, 4, \dots, n + 1$.

It is necessary to estimate the probability that at least one of the two ($n + 2, n - 2$) overstressed unbroken HM fibres, adjacent to the broken HM fibres ($n, -n$) will break. From (5) we obtain the probability that at least one of the two ($n + 2, n - 2$) overstressed HM fibres will break

$$P_{n+2,1} = 2 \frac{d_h}{l_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^{\beta} (K_{n+2}^{\beta} - 1)$$

Now we derive the ratio

$$R_L = \frac{P_{n+2,1}}{P_{n+1,1}^*} = \frac{2}{n+1} R_{P_1} \left(\frac{K_{n+2}^{\beta} - 1}{K_2^{\beta^*} - 1} \right) \quad (13)$$

The LM fibres will fail most likely when $R_L < 1$. In Fig. 3 the calculations of the ratio R_L as the number of broken HM fibres n increases are presented by curve 3. Lower bound on hybrid composite strength σ_{LC} (curve 4) we obtain from σ_{nc} at $R_L = 1$.

5. MODEL OF LAMINATED HYBRID COMPOSITE

The model of unidirectional laminated hybrid composite (Fig. 1b) consists of elastic HM fibre layers and elastic LM fibre layers of equal amount embedded in elastic LM matrix. We see in Fig. 1 that the fibres of each type can be arranged on the sides of squares. The diagonal of the squares presents the model of a single layer hybrid composite. The perimeter of each square presents a belt consisting of the fibres of only one type. Let us number the belts, beginning with the arbitrary one. If it is a HM fibre belt, then 1, 3, 5, ... are HM belts, 2, 4, 6, ... are LM belts. The number of fibres in the belt i is $m_i = 4(i - 1)$ for $i \geq 2$.

The probability, that at least one of m_i fibres of the belt i will break

$$P_{i,1} = 1 - \left(\frac{1 - F(K_{i,0} \sigma)}{1 - F(\sigma)} \right)^{m_i} \quad (14)$$

where $K_{i,0}$ is the stress concentration factor in the fibres of the belt i . $K_{i,0}$ is estimated by shear-lag method [4]. Using (14) we derive

$$R_{P_2} = 2 R_{P_1} \left(\frac{K_{3,0}^{\beta} - 1}{K_{2,0}^{\beta^*} - 1} \right)$$

The possible belt fracture sequences are presented by the tree T (Fig. 2). Each point of the tree T is the probability that certain belt will fail.

The algorithm for searching the most probable belt fracture sequence and computation the tensile strength includes the computation of the probability that the belt i will fail

$$P_{Bi} = \prod_{j=0}^{m_i-1} P_{i,j+1} \quad (15)$$

for $i \geq 2$. $P_{i,j+1}$ is the probability, that fibre $j+1$ of the belt i will fail

$$P_{i,j+1} = 1 - \left(\frac{1 - F(K_{i,j} \mathcal{G})}{1 - F(\mathcal{G})} \right)^{m_i - j} \quad (16)$$

where $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m_i - 1$ is the number of broken fibres of the belt i . When $j = 0$ we obtain the probability $P_{i,1}$ that at least one of m_i fibres of the belt i will fail (14). $K_{i,j}$ is the stress concentration factor in unbroken $m_i - j$ fibres of the belt i when j fibres of the belt i are broken. $K_{i,j}$ is obtained by linear extrapolation from $K_{i,0}$ to $K_{i+2,0}$

$$K_{i,j} = \left(\frac{K_{i+2,0} - K_{i,0}}{m_i} \right) j + K_{i,0} \quad (17)$$

The values of $K_{i+2,0}$ and $K_{i,0}$ we estimate by the shear-lag method solving the set of equilibrium equations for belts [4]. The probability, that a defect of at least n broken belts will occur is

$$P_n = P_1 \prod_{i=2}^n P_{Bi} \quad (18)$$

In order to estimate the stress level \mathcal{G}_{nc} and the strength \mathcal{G}_c we use (9-11).

Upper and lower bound on laminated hybrid composite strength. We derive the corresponding expressions in the same way as for a single layer hybrid composite. For upper bound the belt failure sequence 1, 3, 5 is assumed. We estimate the stress level on laminated hybrid composite \mathcal{G}_{nc} as the number of broken HM fibre belts n increases. From (1, 14-18) we derive the probability P_n that a defect of at least n broken HM belts will occur, and using (9-11) we obtain the stress level on HM fibres at which at least one defect containing a minimum of n broken HM fibre belts will appear with the probability 0.5

$$\mathcal{G}_n = \frac{\langle \mathcal{G} \rangle}{\Gamma(1 + \frac{1}{\beta})} \left(\frac{\ln 2}{MN} \right)^{\frac{1}{\beta(2n-1)^2}} \left[\prod_{i=3,5}^{2n-1} \prod_{j=0}^{4i-5} (4i-j-4) (K_{i,j}^{\beta} - 1) \right]^{\frac{1}{\beta(2n-1)^2}} \quad (19)$$

The corresponding stress level on laminated hybrid composite \mathcal{G}_{nc} we calculate from (11).

For the laminated hybrid we obtain the ratio

$$R_L = \frac{2}{n} R_{P_1} \left(\frac{K_{2n+1,0}^{\beta} - 1}{K_{2,0}^{\beta} - 1} \right)$$

where n is the number of broken HM belts. The LM fibre belts will start to fail when $R_L < 1$. Lower bound on multilayer hybrid composite strength \mathcal{G}_{LC} we obtain from \mathcal{G}_{nc} at $R_L = 1$.

6. APPLICATION OF ANALYSIS TO CROSS-PLY COMPOSITE

Proposed method of analysis can be applied to cross-ply composite composed of layers with different stiffnesses and strengths. Model of cross-ply composite is presented in Fig.4.

Figure 4. Model of cross-ply composite.

Let us number layers beginning with arbitrary one. If it is 90° layer, then 1, 3, -3, 5, -5, ... are 90° layers and 2, -2, 4, -4, ... are 0° layers. Tensile load is applied along the fibres of 0° layers. Transverse cracking in 90° layers is well known phenomenon [10-12]. The strength of 90° layer is assumed to be random variable with the Weibull distribution function [10, 11]

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{\delta_{90^\circ}}{l_0} \left(\frac{\sigma_{90^\circ}}{\sigma_{90^\circ}^0}\right)^\beta\right] \approx \frac{\delta_{90^\circ}}{l_0} \left(\frac{\sigma_{90^\circ}}{\sigma_{90^\circ}^0}\right)^\beta \quad (20)$$

where scale and shape parameters $\sigma_{90^\circ}^0, \beta_{90^\circ}$ are obtained from the experiment in which the crack spacings in 90° layer are measured; δ_{90° is minimum crack spacing at which the tensile cracking stress restore 0.9 of its initial value. For glass fibre cross-ply laminate [10] $\beta_{90^\circ} \approx 8$, for carbon fibre cross-ply laminate [11] $\beta = 6+11$. The strength of fibres of 0° layer comply with the Weibull law [5-8] (formula 2). In this case the minimum crack spacing δ_0 is the fibre ineffective length in 0° layer. Minimum crack spacings $\delta_{90^\circ}, \delta_0$ as well as stress concentration initiated by cracks are calculated using shear-lag method [4].

It is clear that various layer failure sequences may occur between the two extreme cases: a) alternately 90° layers and 0° layers break in succession 1, 2, -2, 3, -3, 4, -4, ..., b) only 90° layers break 1, 3, -3, 5, -5, 7, -7. Fracture modes of cross-ply composite can be presented by the tree graph \mathbf{T} (Fig. 2). In the same way as for hybrid composite we derive expressions R_{p_1}, R_{p_2} . For $R_{p_1} > 1, R_{p_2} > 1$ more likely is matrix cracking in 90° layer than fibre breaking in 0° layer. To find the most probable layer failure sequence and to calculate the strength of cross-ply composite the algorithm of search is used. The strength determined by only 90° layer failure gives the upper bound on cross-ply composite strength. The stress level at which the overstressed 0° layers are

expected to break represents a lower bound on cross-ply composite strength. Calculations have been made for $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_{11}$ composite laminate with the following parameters [6]: fibre Young's modulus $E_f = 420$ GPa, matrix shear modulus $G_m = 1.26$ GPa, Young's modulus of 0° layer $E_{0^\circ} = 160$ GPa, Young's modulus of 90° layer $E_{90^\circ} = 38$ GPa, strength of fibres in 0° layer at ineffective length $\langle G_{f0^\circ} \rangle = 4$ GPa, strength of 90° layer $\langle G_{90^\circ} \rangle = 0.1$ GPa, fibre volume fraction in 0° and 90° layers $V_f = 0.34$, Weibull's shape parameters $\beta_{90^\circ} = 6$, $\beta_{0^\circ} = 6$. The results of calculations are presented in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Stress level on cross-ply composite σ_{nc} (1, 2, 4) and ratio R_L (curve 3) as the number of broken 90° layers n increases.

- 1 - upper bound on strength
- 2 - calculations using algorithm of search
- 4 - lower bound on strength

7. CLOSURE

It is shown, that the initial failure of LM fibres is of small probability and at the beginning the HM fibre breaks are accumulated. The possible fibre break propagation ways may occur between the two extreme cases: a) alternately HM fibres and LM fibres break b) only HM fibres break. The algorithm for searching the most probable fibre break propagation way and computation of the strength and the fibre damage level of a hybrid composite is developed. The stress level at which the overstressed LM fibres are expected to break represents a lower bound on the hybrid composite strength. The ultimate damage level of HM fibres in a hybrid composite is much higher than the damage level of HM fibres in a HM fibre composite. The hybrid effect for composite strength is negative. Proposed method of analysis is applied to cross-ply composite.

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